

Environmental Quality Index (EQI): An Intuitive Indicator to Evaluate the Environmental Quality Over Time

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 28, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Environmental Quality Index (EQI), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Ecological Footprints, Load Factor Capacity, Asian Economies</p>	<p><i>Current environmental indicators assess environmental quality, but there is no single indicator that measures the overall environmental quality of a country, state, or region in an easy and intuitive methodology. This paper provides a simple but informative indicator known as the Environmental Quality Index (EQI) for 48 Asian. The EQI represents a step towards clarity by combining CO2 emissions, Methane emissions, nitrous oxide emissions, Ecological Footprint, and load factor capacity data into one indicator. Contrary to other indices, the EQI does not use complex mathematical procedures but is designed for simplicity, which facilitates understanding and applying economics to professionals and laymen. This paper offers a simple but informative measure known as the Environmental Quality Index (EQI) of Asian countries for the period from 1996 to 2020. We adopt PCA (Principal Component Analysis) to maximize ease of understanding. In addition to Raw EQI, which gives equal weightings to its components, we build weighted EQI's and show that the two indices behave similarly to the Asian data.</i></p>
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Introduction

Over the past few decades, the pursuit of higher growth and economic prosperity has been a central goal of government policies. However, to achieve greater growth, natural resources are needed, which has a negative impact on the environment. Therefore, the achievement of sustainable development and continuous improvement of the current quality of life at a lower intensity of resource utilization without jeopardizing future generations has received more global attention than ever before, particularly considering global warming, climate change, and other environmental problems are getting increasingly serious. Understanding and forecasting changes in environmental quality is a crucial topic for policymakers in charge of environmental policies. The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) is a hypothesis widely used in the Environmental Economics literature for modelling the growth path of the environment empirically. The EKC hypothesis is that there is an inverted U-relation between environmental degradation and per capita income. In other words, environmental degradation is projected to increase with income to a certain extent, after which a higher per capita income will improve environmental quality. Many studies have focused on the contrast between the short run and long-term effects of economic growth, although the research on economic development and environmental deterioration is misleading. In specifically, the notion that, despite short-term environmental degradation, long-term economic expansion can enhance environmental quality. The Environmental Kuznets Curve is the name given to this phenomenon (EKC). However, mixed evidence exists for this feature of economic growth and the environment. For example, by considering different countries and group of countries different empirical work reported contrasting outcomes on the validity of EKC (Apergis, 2016; Caviglia-Harris et al., 2009; Lantz & Feng, 2006; Lindmark, 2002; Narayan & Narayan, 2010; Nasir et al., 2019; Onafowora & Owoye, 2014; Sencer Atasoy, 2017; Song et al., 2013). One can argue that potential differences exist between developed and developing countries. However, such disagreement would be simplified as the empirical evidence indicates significant differences, even within developed and developing sectors (Abbasi & Riaz, 2016; Ahmed et al., 2021; Chang, 2014; Jalil & Feridun, 2011; Javid & Sharif, 2016; Shahbaz et al., 2018; Solarin et al., 2017; Tamazian et al., 2009; Tamazian & Bhaskara Rao, 2010; Zakaria & Bibi, 2019). At the same time, it is necessary to carry out a detailed analysis, specific to the economy concerned, before drawing a conclusion on ecological consequences of economic growth.

According to the BP PLC Global Energy Statistical Study, emissions from Asian economies more than doubled between 2000 and 2008, from about 3.4 gigatons to 7.4 gigatons. Over the past several years, the rate of increase in emissions has slowed. According to BP, China's emissions growth rate be around 2.6 percent between 2008

and 2018. Carbon dioxide emissions have decreased since 2011, reaching their lowest level in 2020 since 2011. There are the largest decreases in both energy demand and carbon emissions since World War II, according to historical standards. Indeed, CO₂ emissions decreased by more than 2 Gt last year, returning to levels last seen in 2011. To put it another way, if carbon emissions continue to decline at the same rate as they did last year over the next 30 years, global carbon emissions will have decreased by nearly 85% by 2050 (*Statistical Review of World Energy Globally Consistent Data on World Energy Markets and Authoritative Publications in the Field of Energy*, 2021). As the trends in Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission, methane emission (ME), and nitrous oxide (NO) emissions of Asian economies are reported in Figure 1. While the trends in Ecological Footprints (EFP), and load factor capacity (LFC) of the under-analysis economies are reported in figure 2. Given that Asian economies has been emitting greenhouse gases along with substantial economic growth, it is intriguing to explicate the environmental consequences of growth by constructing an instinctive indicator namely EQI (Environmental Quality Index) for assessing a country's environmental quality. So, the main objective of this work to construct the EQI by adopting the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) procedure of assigning weight. The remaining paper is organized as next section conclude the outcomes of previous studies done to trace the impact of different macroeconomic dimensions on environmental quality by taking different indicators. Section 3 provide the estimates about the construction of Environmental Quality Index. The final section reserved to conclude and present policy recommendations.

Figure: 1 Trends in CO₂/ ME / NO

Source: World Development Indicators

Figure: 2 Trends in EFP & LFC

Source: Global Footprint Network

From this point of view, the paper aimed to provide an intuitive environmental indicator by building the EQI for the 48 Asian economies. The novelty of the study lies in the construction of Environmental Quality Index (EQI) for 48 Asian economies. In doing so we have utilized the PCA (Principal Component Analysis) for the construction of EQI. The list of Asian countries is reported in table A1 in appendix.

The development of this article begins with a brief overview of the existing indicators and their shortcomings. We then introduce the EQI and explain how indicators are constructed to achieve raw scores and efficiency ratings to measure a country's environmental quality. To demonstrate how the index has performed over different economic periods, we review 48 Asian economies environmental and economic history from 1996 to 2020, including the EQI results for each year.

Existing Literature on Environmental quality

Economic growth is the main goal of macroeconomic policy, especially after the 2nd World War (Raworth, Doughnut, 2017). The same applies to Asian economies. The impact of economic growth on the environment is an important aspect that has attracted the attention of the world over the past decades. Several studies have explored the effects of economic growth on environmental degradation in this setting, with an emphasis on the idea of EKC. According to EKC, economic growth and environmental degradation have a U-shaped negative relationship. Economic expansion adds to environmental degradation in the near run. When the country's income rises, however, this ratio reverses and economic growth begins to slow, which is good for the environment. Following the initial contributions of (Grossman et al., 1991) to the relationship between growth and the environment in the context of EKC, there are few studies that have investigated experimentally with this relationship. For instance, (Fosten et al., 2012) reported important evidence on EKC. In addition, they found disproportionate corrections for the long-term EKC transitional imbalances, which they attributed to the UK's stringent environmental regulations. Perhaps this is an interesting aspect for developing countries such as ASEAN. In a separate study, by taking the sample of Spanish data (Sephton & Mann, 2013), observed that the EKC did not follow the inverted U-shaped model. It appears that long-term economic growth leads to lower carbon dioxide emissions and therefore environmental improvements. In a follow-up study for Spain as well, (Esteve & Tamarit, 2012) found that long-term non-linear pull factors do exist overall emissions and per capita income and asymmetric adjustments. The same is true of Nasir et al., (2019) and Shahbaz et al., (2018) report on the short- and longer-term relationship between economic growth and the environment. In contrast, although (Ghosh, 2010) focuses on the Indian economy, he notes that there is no evidence of a long-term relationship between economic growth and emissions. In a different study, involving committee members from 27 industrialized countries, the Solarin et al., 2017) reported significant evidence of an EKC relationship. Likewise, in a study conducted in Arctic countries, (Salahuddin et al., 2018) reported that there is little evidence of EKC in Arctic countries. However, only evidence from the EKC could be found in Japan and South Korea, the only developed countries in their datasets. Charfeddine & Ben Khediri, 2016) maintained that the developmental stages of the state can also influence the existence of an EKC.

The existing literature provide contrasting and inconclusive results regarding the impact of macroeconomic variables on environmental quality. So, it is important to derive an inclusive and comprehensive indicator to measure environmental quality of the Asian countries.

Construction of Environmental Quality Index (EQI)

Despite recent developments in environmental science, many people are still uninformed about the theory of the background environment and the confusion caused by the abundance of economic statistics in the media. Furthermore, many people are unable to properly evaluate their country's current environmental performance and compare it to historical performance. In other words, they cannot situate current performance in a historic context. This problem is caused by several factors, including:

- The number of environmental statistics used by businesses and governments, their quality and potential differences in media coverage.
- An absence of historic background needed to portray and deliver the environmental movements.
- An absence of context regarding alternative statistics, for instance not all statistics area unit created equal, with some clearly being a lot of necessary and consequential than others.

The Environmental Quality Index (EQI) is designed to resolve these issues. Although structurally easy, the EQI could be a powerful Environmental indicator that clearly measures the performance of the economy's all primary segments: households, firms, government, and available geographical area. The EQI includes variables that influence all sectors simultaneously:

- the Carbon dioxide emissions
- the Nitrous oxide emissions
- the Methane emissions
- Ecological footprints
- Load Factor Capacity

Data their descriptions and sources are summarized in table 1.

Table 1
Dimensions of Environmental Quality Index (EQI)

<i>Environmental Quality</i>	Indicators	Definition	Data Sources
Emissions	CO ₂	CO ₂ emissions (metric tons per capita)	WDI (World Development Indicators)
	ME	Methane emissions in energy sector (thousand metric tons of	

Demand & supply of Environment		CO2 equivalent)	
	NO	Nitrous oxide emissions in energy sector (thousand metric tons of CO2 equivalent)	WDI (World Development Indicators)
	EFP	Ecological footprints (No of Earth (gha per person)	Global Footprint Network
	LFC	Ecological Footprint vs Biocapacity (gha per person)	

Source: Own elaboration

Note that after selecting the weights for the indicators of environmental quality the environmental quality index is defined as follows:

$$EQI = \frac{[W_1(CO_2) + W_2(NO) + W_3(ME) + W_4(EFP) + W_5(LFC)] - \text{Min Value}}{\text{Max Value} - \text{Min Value}} \quad (1)$$

Table: 2 Environmental Quality Index (EQI)

Principal Component Estimates

Variables	PC_1	PC_2	PC_3	PC_4	PC_5	Normal weights
CO_2	0.66	-0.08	0.21	0.05	0.71	0.58
ME	0.09	0.69	0.16	-0.69	-0.02	0.10
NO	0.07	0.70	-0.09	0.69	-0.01	0.08
EFP	0.65	-0.09	0.27	0.06	-0.69	0.57
LFC	-0.35	-0.01	0.91	0.17	0.04	0.31
Eigenvalues	2.05	1.67	0.86	0.30	0.10	
Cumulative	0.41	0.74	0.91	0.97	1.00	
Variations						

Source Own Construction

In this stage, we applied PCA to the five indicators of environment (Carbon dioxide emission, Nitrous oxide emission, Methane emissions, Ecological footprint, and Load factor capacity) to compute their weights in the overall index. Table 2 shows the main component composition and normalized weights for each dimension for Asian economies over the period of 1996 to 2020. The final column shows that PCA determines the maximum carbon dioxide emissions weight (0.58), followed by ecological footprint (0.57), load factor capacity (0.31), methane emission (0.10), and nitrous oxide emission (0.08). From this information, carbon dioxide emission, and ecological footprint are the most important dimensions in explaining the level of environmental quality of Asian economies.

Regarding the structure of the main components, we found that the first and most important components, which accounted for 41 percent of the total data change (see section of Table 2), contributed equally across all three dimensions. As previously explained, this needs to be maintained to ensure that all three dimensions measure the same latent structure, which is interpreted as the degree of environmental quality. It shows that in most cases only the first component accounts for more than 90% of the total variation in the causal variable. Therefore, a strategy that uses only the first major component can be a good approach to assessing the dimensions and levels of environmental quality. In the last section of table 2, cumulative variances for EQI are provided, expressing the changes in the indices that are explained by the relevant dimensions. The first component of the environmental quality dimension, carbon dioxide emission, accounts for 41% of the total differences in this dimension (see table 2). In the structure of environmental quality, the second component adds the 33% information. The third, fourth, and fifth components, on the other hand, increased financial inclusion information by 17 percent, 6%, and 3%, respectively. The correlation matrix of the different dimensions of environmental quality are reported in table A2 in appendix.

In contrast to ecological footprint and load factor capacity, nitrous oxide and methane emissions give some of its information to the second component, so that this dimension not only contributes to the overall index through the first main component, but also adds additional information through the second component and becomes relevant for the second component of the overall Index.

Ranking of Asian countries based on their EQI scores for the year of 2020 are reported in table and figure 3. Based on EQI scores for the year 2020 Qatar having the highest position according to environmental quality index and Timor Leste showing the lowest position among the 48 Asian economies. Overall, the developed Asian economies showing better environmental quality as compare to the low-income Asian economies.

Table: 3

EQI Based Ranking of Asian Countries

Country	Rank	Country	Rank
Qatar	1	Vietnam	25
UAE	2	Bhutan	26
Kuwait	3	Uzbekistan	27
Bahrain	4	India	28
Oman	5	Azerbaijan	29
Brunei	6	Georgia	30
South Korea	7	Armenia	31
China	8	Indonesia	32
Saudi Arabia	9	Lao PDR	33
Russia	10	Sri Lanka	34
Singapore	11	Philippines	35
Kazakhstan	12	Syria	36
Turkmenistan	13	Turkey	37
Taiwan	14	Kyrgyzstan	38
Israel	15	Maldives	39
Japan	16	Pakistan	40
Mongolia	17	Nepal	41
Iran	18	Tajikistan	42
Cyprus	19	Bangladesh	43
Malaysia	20	Afghanistan	44
Lebanon	21	Cambodia	45
Iraq	22	Myanmar	46
Thailand	23	Yemen	47
Jordan	24	Timor-Leste	48

Source: own elaboration

Rank → based on the year 2020 scores

Figure: 3

EQI based Position of Asian Economies

Source: Own elaboration

Note: The ranking is made on the basis of scores of Asian economies for the year of 2020

1 → Best Environmental Quality and 48 → Worst Environmental Quality

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

Environmental quality is an important part of economic development. The right of policy makers to use environmental services to prevent environmental damage should be a priority. However, efforts to measure environmental quality are still small and incomplete. Environmental quality is a multi-dimensional concept that cannot be captured precisely by individual indicators but is determined by a much larger set of indicators than some of the indicators accounted for in the existing work. The nature of environmental quality is complex and heterogeneous. An inclusive ecosystem must promote the growth and development of the most vulnerable groups in society. that is, they are most affected by ecosystem constraints.

Existing indicators for environmental quality are questionable because they provided inconclusive results. This paper proposes a one-step PCA to measure the level of environmental quality index for Asian countries or region. This method is statistically good for indexing and reliable for large amounts of data. We measure environmental quality using a composite index for 48 Asian economies, using five causal variables as determinants of environmental quality for the period from 1996-2020. This index can be compared across countries and over time. In particular, our index states that the level of environmental quality is determined by maximizing the ecological absorption and reproductive capacity of the nature and minimizing the carbon dioxide, nitrous oxide and methane emissions. Our main contributions are to create a comprehensive index for environmental quality that covers both Supply and demand information of eco system.

As our assessment shows, carbon dioxide emissions and ecological footprint are the most important dimension in determining environmental quality of Asian economies. The index is useful for explaining the determinants of environmental quality and its contribution to economic growth and development. Our index is easy to interpret and calculate. We believe that more detailed information on various dimensions in the form of disaggregated greenhouse emissions data, frequency of use, ecological footprint, and load factor capacity information can be useful for a more accurate assessment of environmental quality, leading to policy recommendations.

Appendix

Table: A1

List of Asian Countries

Afghanistan	Timor-Leste	Thailand
Syria	Uzbekistan	Turkey
Tajikistan	Vietnam	Turkmenistan
Yemen	Armenia	Bahrain
Bangladesh	Azerbaijan	Brunei Darussalam
Bhutan	China	Cyprus
Cambodia	Georgia	Israel
India	Indonesia	Japan
Kyrgyzstan	Iran	Kuwait

Lao PDR	Iraq	Oman
Magnolia	Jordan	Qatar
Myanmar	Kazakhstan	Saudi Arabia
Nepal	Lebanon	Singapore
Pakistan	Malaysia	Korea republic
Philippines	Maldives	Taiwan
Sri Lanka	Russian federation	United Arab Emirates

Source: Own elaboration

Table: A2

Correlation Matrix of the Dimensions of Financial Inclusion

Variables	CO2	ME	NO	EFP	LFC
CO2	1.000000				
ME	0.049039	1.000000			
NO	-0.008573	0.678996	1.000000		
EFP	0.896795	0.038239	-0.029320	1.000000	
LFC	-0.311184	0.023830	-0.100248	-0.262364	1.000000

Source: Own elaboration

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